

Exploring Micro-Sized Zirconium Trisulfide with Quasi-1D Layered Structure as a Low-Potential, Ultrahigh-Rate Anode Material for Lithium-Ion Batteries: Structural and Reaction Mechanism Insights

Shuangying Wei^{a*}, Min Liu^b, Ruizhi Yu^c, Haoyang Jiang^d, Huaijuan Zhou^e, Heng Li^a, Min Li^{a,f}, Payal Chauhan^a, Bing Wu^a, Takeshi Matsuo^g, Kseniia Mosina^a, Lukas Dekanovsky^a, Filipa M. Oliveira^a, Jan Luxa^a, Ondrej Jankovsky^a, Jincang Su^{d*}, Zdeněk Sofer^{a*}

^a *Department of Inorganic Chemistry, University of Chemistry and Technology Prague, Technická 5, 16628 Prague 6, Czech Republic*

^b *College of New Energy, Ningbo University of Technology, Ningbo 315336, Zhejiang, China*

^c *Institute of Micro/Nano Materials and Devices, Ningbo University of Technology, Ningbo, Zhejiang 315211, China*

^d *School of Materials Science and Engineering, Xiangtan University, Xiangtan 411105, China*

^e *Advanced Research Institute of Multidisciplinary Sciences, Beijing Institute of Technology, Beijing 100081, China*

^f *School of Physics, Xi'an Jiaotong University, Xi'an 710049, China*

^g *Department of Mechanical Engineering, Okayama University, 3-chōme-1 Tsushimanaka, Kita Ward, Okayama, Japan*

Corresponding authors: weis@vscht.cz; sujc@xtu.edu.cn; zdenek.sofer@vscht.cz

Abstract

Materials from the Group IVB transition metal trichalcogenides (TMTCs) family, such as zirconium trisulfide (ZrS₃), have attracted significant attention for lithium-ion battery (LIB) applications due to their tunable band gaps, anisotropic conductivity, and high specific capacities. While several theoretical and experimental studies have focused on the synthesis and physicochemical properties of ZrS₃, investigations into their lithium-ion storage properties have

been limited. Herein, micro-sized ZrS_3 with a quasi-one-dimensional (quasi-1D) layered structure prepared using a straightforward solid-state reaction, were synthesized and evaluated as anode materials for LIBs to understand their electrochemical reaction mechanisms and structural evolution. Galvanostatic charge/discharge and cyclic voltammetry tests at various discharge depths (1.0, 0.3, and 0.001 V) were performed to characterize the transition between intercalation and conversion reactions. After 40 cycles, the ZrS_3 electrodes displayed a high discharge capacity of 844 mAh g^{-1} at a current density of 40 mA g^{-1} . In addition, they exhibited excellent rate capability, delivering a capacity of 281 mAh g^{-1} at a high current density of 3000 mA g^{-1} by the 40th cycle, along with remarkable long-term cycling stability over 2300 cycles, maintaining a stable capacity of 408 mAh g^{-1} . Furthermore, structural changes and surface evolution in the ZrS_3 electrodes, observed under various electrochemical states through *ex-situ* characterization including XRD, SEM-EDX (with cross-sectional analysis), XPS and EIS, providing detailed insights into the electrochemical reaction processes. DFT calculations further elucidated the Li-ion diffusion pathways and energy barriers in both bulk and monolayer ZrS_3 , revealing intrinsic structural advantages that facilitate superior electrochemical performance. Our comprehensive study, combining detailed experimental analysis with theoretical insights, provides critical guidance for exploring electrochemical capabilities and rationally designing advanced Group IVB TMTC-based anode materials for alkali-ion batteries.

Keywords: Layered materials; Zirconium trisulfide; Electrochemical reaction mechanisms; Structural evolution; Lithium-ion batteries

1. Introduction

Lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) are currently the most prevalent energy storage technology, widely applied in portable electronics and electric vehicles (EVs), with growing interest in large-scale grid

energy systems ¹. Their widespread adoption stems from key advantages such as high energy density, long cycle life, efficient energy conversion, and low self-discharge rates ². However, as the global demand for safer, more efficient, and high-performance energy storage solutions continues to grow, advancing LIB technology remains a critical priority ^{3,4}. One of the most important performance parameters in LIBs is rate capability, which determines the ability to sustain high charge/discharge currents without significant capacity loss ⁵⁻⁸. This capability is influenced by multiple factors, including electronic and ionic transport, interface charge transfer, desolvation processes, as well as electrode architecture and electrolyte composition. Among these, ionic diffusion within the bulk electrode is frequently a rate-limiting step, though charge transfer kinetics at the electrode-electrolyte interface can also play a critical role ^{9,10}. To address this limitation, extensive research has focused on nanostructured electrode designs that reduce ion diffusion distances and improve charge transport kinetics ^{11,12}. However, such complex nanoarchitectures often come with trade-offs, including reduced volumetric energy density, structural instability, higher manufacturing costs, and environmental concerns ^{13,14}. An alternative approach is to explore and characterize unique crystal structures that inherently facilitate fast Li⁺ insertion and extraction, thereby achieving both ultrahigh-rate capability and long-term stability without compromising other key battery metrics ^{15,16}.

Recently, mixed titanium-niobium oxides (*e.g.*, TiNb₂O₇) have been explored as high-rate anode materials due to their three-dimensional (3D) interconnected tunnel structures that enable rapid Li⁺ diffusion ¹⁷. However, their relatively high operating potentials (>1.5 V vs. Li⁺/Li) limit the full-cell voltage and energy density when paired with conventional cathodes. Thus, there is an urgent need to develop novel rigid host lattices that combine low operating potentials with high-rate performance ¹⁸.

Transition-metal chalcogenides (TMCs) have attracted considerable interest due to their tunable bandgap, high surface area, and excellent electrical conductivity^{19–22}. However, despite their early design potential for rechargeable LIBs, transition-metal trichalcogenides (TMTCs) have received comparatively little attention in this field^{23,24}. These materials typically display quasi-one-dimensional (quasi-1D) or layered structures, following the general formula MX_3 , where M represents a group IVB (Ti, Zr, Hf) or VB (Nb, Ta) transition metal, and X is a group VIA (S, Se, Te) chalcogen^{25,26}. Structurally, TMTCs consist of strong covalent bonds along 1D atomic chains, while adjacent chains are held together by van der Waals (vdW) interactions, imparting both quasi-1D and layered characteristics²⁷. The fundamental structural unit is a 1D chain of MX_3 prisms, which gives rise to distinct electronic and mechanical properties²⁸. The physical properties of MX_3 compounds span a broad range, from superconducting to semiconducting, and even highly insulating, depending on the stacking sequence and interchain interactions^{29–31}.

Among these materials, zirconium trisulfide (ZrS_3) has received limited attention regarding both its chemical and physical properties, with only a handful of theoretical studies available³². The structural and transport properties of ZrS_3 were first extensively studied by Professor Jean Rouxel in the late 1980s³³. His pioneering work laid the foundation for understanding the quasi-1D channel structure of ZrS_3 , which was recognized as a key feature enabling enhanced ion diffusion and electrochemical stability^{34,35}. These attributes position ZrS_3 as a promising candidate for high-capacity and long-cycle anode materials in next-generation LIBs. ZrS_3 exhibits a unique layered structure, in which vdW interactions between layers facilitate efficient Li-ion intercalation and diffusion^{36,37}. Unlike conventional 2D TMDCs (*e.g.*, MoS_2 , WS_2), which rely primarily on interlayer spacing for Li-ion storage, ZrS_3 integrates both chain-like and layered motifs, providing additional Li-ion storage sites^{38,39}. This structural duality promotes fast Li-ion insertion/extraction,

leading to superior rate capability and long-term cycling stability⁴⁰. Furthermore, at low voltages, ZrS₃ undergoes a conversion reaction, allowing additional Li-ion uptake and enhanced capacity retention^{41,42}. Despite these advantages, the reaction mechanisms and electrochemical behavior of ZrS₃ have remained largely unexplored both experimentally and theoretically until this study. Herein, micro-sized quasi-1D ZrS₃ microbelts were prepared through a facile solid-state reaction and their morphology and structural properties were systematically examined using X-ray diffraction (XRD), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), transmission electron microscopy (TEM), and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS). For the first time, we evaluated the electrochemical performance of ZrS₃ as an anode material for LIBs, analyzing how its reaction mechanisms shift between intercalation and conversion processes at different cut-off voltages (1.0, 0.3, and 0.001 V). Impressively, even without carbon decoration or nanostructuring, micro-sized ZrS₃ demonstrates excellent lithium storage properties, including high specific capacity, superior rate capability, and long-cycle stability up to 2300 cycles. Morphological and compositional changes were monitored using *ex-situ* XRD, SEM, SEM-EDX, cross-section SEM, XPS and EIS. Additionally, density functional theory (DFT) calculations revealed that Li-ion diffusion in bulk ZrS₃ follows a pathway between adjacent stable H sites across T sites, with a relatively low energy barrier of 0.12 eV, enabling fast Li-ion transport and high charge–discharge rates. Furthermore, lithiated bulk ZrS₃ exhibits a significantly enhanced Young’s modulus compared to its pristine state, indicating excellent mechanical stability during lithiation and delithiation cycles. These findings highlight the potential of micro-sized ZrS₃ as a promising low-potential, ultrahigh-rate anode material for high-performance LIBs. Furthermore, the study provides new insights into the reaction mechanisms of ZrS₃, offering valuable perspectives for future advancements in group IVB TMTCs for next-generation energy storage applications.

2. Discussion

ZrS₃ is a typical transition metal trisulfide, with its structure consisting of both disulfide (S₂²⁻) and sulfide (S²⁻) anions⁴³. The fundamental building blocks of ZrS₃ are 1D chains, where Zr⁴⁺ cations are coordinated with these anions⁴⁴. These chains are covalently bonded along their lengths, forming stable 1D structures. Through weak van der Waals-like interactions, these 1D chains assemble into 2D layers⁴⁵, characterized by an interlayer spacing of 9.01 Å, as depicted in **Fig. 1a**. The 2D layers then stack through additional van der Waals interactions, resulting in a bulk crystal with a prismatic morphology. This unique stacking mechanism results in a layered structure, where the interlayer forces are significantly weaker than the covalent bonds within the chains⁴⁶.

A thorough set of material characterizations was carried out to understand the structural, chemical, and morphological properties of ZrS₃. The powder XRD pattern (**Fig. 1b**) confirms the successful synthesis of phase-pure ZrS₃ (JCPDS No. 30-1498), which crystallizes in a monoclinic structure with the space group P2₁/m³⁴. Notably, no discernible impurity peaks were observed, indicating the high purity of the material. The characteristic diffraction peaks observed at 10.13°, 19.86°, 31.82°, 35.41°, 40.68°, 43.6°, 50.30°, and 62.49° correspond to the (001), (002), (012), (-201), (004), (-211), (020) and (311) planes, respectively^{47,48}. The Raman spectrum for ZrS₃ (**Fig. 1c**) exhibits four active Raman modes at 149, 276, 314, and 525 cm⁻¹⁴⁹. The pronounced Raman peak at 525 cm⁻¹ is attributed to the stretching mode of the (S-S)²⁻ group⁵⁰. Additionally, a peak at 457 cm⁻¹ is considered to be a combination peak arising from excessive sulfide species, while the peak at 353 cm⁻¹ is attributed to second-order scattering effect⁵¹. XPS confirms the chemical composition and oxidation states of the elements present in ZrS₃. The high-resolution Zr 3d XPS spectra (**Fig. 1d**) reveals two prominent peaks at 181.3±0.1 eV and 183.7±0.1 eV, which correspond to Zr⁴⁺⁵². The low spectrum displays the Zr 3d_{3/2} and Zr 3d_{5/2} peaks of ZrO_x, located at 183.0±0.1 eV and 185.4±0.1 eV, respectively. The spin-orbit doublet splittings for ZrS₃ and

ZrO_x are 2.4 eV⁵³, confirming the presence of a thin surface oxide layer on the ZrS₃ microbelts. Similarly, the XPS S 2p spectra (**Fig. 1e**) reveal the coexistence of sulfide (S²⁻) and disulfide (S₂²⁻) species, fitted using two distinct doublet peaks. The binding energies of the S 2p_{1/2} and S 2p_{3/2} peaks for sulfide are 162.3±0.1 eV and 162.9±0.1 eV, respectively, whereas those for the disulfide group appear at 163.4±0.1 eV and 163.9±0.1 eV⁵⁴. The textural properties of ZrS₃ were analyzed using the Brunauer–Emmett–Teller (BET) method, revealing a specific surface area of 3.505 m² g⁻¹, a total pore volume of 0.0065 cm³ g⁻¹, and an average pore size of 4.038 nm (**Table S1, Fig. 1f**). The BET results indicate a relatively low specific surface area (3.505 m² g⁻¹) and limited pore volume (0.0065 cm³ g⁻¹), suggesting a compact and dense morphology, typical of bulk layered sulfides. Nevertheless, the observed average pore size of 4.038 nm falls within the mesoporous range (2–50 nm), implying the presence of a limited number of mesopores. While not abundant, such pores, together with interlayer gaps, may still facilitate lithium-ion transport and electrolyte penetration⁵⁵. These structural features are expected to synergize with the layered architecture of ZrS₃, supporting fast ion diffusion and stable cycling behavior^{56,57}.

Fig. 1 (a) Schematic illustration of the crystal structure of ZrS₃; (b) XRD pattern of ZrS₃; (c) Raman spectra of ZrS₃; (d) High-resolution XPS spectra of ZrS₃: Zr 3*d*, (e) S 2*p* core levels; (f) pore size distribution and N₂ adsorption–desorption isotherm (insert) curve of ZrS₃.

The SEM images in **Fig. 2a** exhibit a well-defined belt-like structure with smooth surfaces and a layered morphology. These microbelts have relatively high aspect ratios, likely due to the intrinsic anisotropic growth of ZrS₃ crystals along the quasi-1D direction^{58,59}. The belt length ranges from 15 to 50 μm, with thicknesses varying between 1 to 10 μm. The SEM-EDX analysis confirms the uniform distribution of Zr and S, as depicted in **Fig. 2a**, validating the composition and purity of the ZrS₃ sample. Upon further investigation using TEM, the microbelt structure transforms into exfoliated ZrS₃ nanoribbons. This transition can be attributed to the weak vdW interactions between adjacent layers, which makes ZrS₃ highly susceptible to exfoliation under ultra-sonication or sample preparation processes⁶⁰.

As revealed by SEM and TEM observations (**Fig. 2**), the synthesized ZrS₃ exhibits a typical nanoribbon morphology with a high aspect ratio, characterized by micrometer-scale lengths and sub-micrometer widths. The TEM image (**Fig. 2b**) reveals the strip-like morphology of an exfoliated ZrS₃ nanoribbon, where regions of varying contrast correspond to differences in thickness⁶¹. The high-resolution TEM (HRTEM) images (**Fig. 2c** and **e**) further confirm the well-defined lattice fringes of ZrS₃ nanoribbons⁶². The measured interplanar spacing from **Fig. 2c** is approximately 0.47 nm, which matches well with the (−101) plane of monoclinic ZrS₃ (JCPDS No. 30-1498, *d* = 0.4677 nm). In contrast, **Fig. 2e** shows a spacing of 0.34 nm, corresponding to the (−102) plane (*d* = 0.3582 nm). These observations reveal the high crystallinity of the synthesized material and the presence of multiple exposed facets, which may promote lithium-ion

diffusion and enhance structural stability during cycling. Additionally, the selected area electron diffraction (SAED) pattern (**Fig. 2d**) exhibits a well-defined set of diffraction spots, indicating the single-crystalline nature of the nanoribbon structure⁶³. These multi-scale structural characterizations confirm the successful synthesis of high-quality layered ZrS_3 with a quasi-1D building unit and ribbon-like morphology, providing a robust structural foundation for further electrochemical investigation.

Fig. 2 (a) SEM images of ZrS_3 at different magnifications with corresponding EDX mappings; (b) TEM, (c, e) HRTEM images, and (d) SAED patterns of ZrS_3 .

The electrochemical insertion/extraction and conversion mechanisms of the ZrS₃ electrode were initially investigated through cyclic voltammetry (CV) measurements at a scan rate of 0.2 mV s⁻¹ over the first three cycles, exploring different voltage windows of 1.0–3.0 V, 0.3–3.0 V, and 0.001–3.0 V, respectively (**Fig. 3a–c**). The cathodic and anodic peaks in the CV results indicate multi-step intercalation and conversion reactions involving the layered ZrS₃ electrode⁶⁴. Specifically, these processes involve the insertion of Li⁺ into the ZrS₃ layered structure, leading to changes in the sulfur electronic environment and the reduction of S₂²⁻ to S²⁻⁶⁵. It is important to note that during the first scan across voltage range of 1.0–3.0 V (**Fig. 3a**), two key electrochemical characteristics are observed: (i) a reduction peak near 1.8 V and (ii) a corresponding oxidation peak near 2.0 V. These reversible peaks are indicative of the reversible Li⁺ intercalation and extraction within the ZrS₃ structure, as described by **Equation 1**.

The slight separation between the reduction and oxidation peaks is attributed to polarization, and the two distinct plateaus in the charge/discharge curves (**Fig. 3d**) correspond to phase transitions during Li⁺ intercalation/extraction⁶⁶. For the voltage window of 0.3 to 3.0 V, multiple oxidation peaks appear during the initial anodic sweep (**Fig. 3b**), reflecting the stepwise nature of the reversible conversion process, as shown by **Equation 2**.

As the depth of discharge increases in the first cycle, peaks appear around 0.8 V, which are primarily associated with conversion reactions, while SEI formation occurs at lower voltages (<0.5 V)⁶⁷. In the anodic scan, peaks near 1.1 V suggest partial oxidation of Li₂S and Zr to ZrS₃, indicating that the ZrS₃ structure can partially recover during cycling⁶⁸. In subsequent scans of the voltage window of 0.3 to 3.0 V, the CV curves exhibit well-defined cathodic and anodic peaks,

suggesting a moderate degree of reversibility in the phase transformations during lithiation/delithiation. For the voltage window of 0.001 to 3.0 V (**Fig. 3c**), as the depth of discharge increases, peaks appear around 0.2 V, which are associated with deep conversion reactions⁶⁹. In the anodic scan, peaks near 0.6 V suggest partial oxidation of Li_2S , contributing to some reversibility⁷⁰. Additionally, the persistence of these peaks in subsequent cycles suggests a relatively high degree of reversibility for the insertion/extraction and conversion processes, though capacity fading may still occur due to SEI growth and incomplete conversion⁷¹.

To elucidate the electrochemical mechanisms of ZrS_3 electrodes, galvanostatic discharge/charge measurements were conducted across three voltage ranges: 1.0–3.0 V, 0.3–3.0 V, and 0.001–3.0 V (**Fig. 3d–f, 3g–i**). In the 1.0–3.0 V range, as shown in **Fig. 3d**, lithium intercalation is the dominant mechanism, with initial discharge and charge capacities of 461 mAh g^{-1} and 37.4 mAh g^{-1} , respectively. The significant irreversible capacity loss, likely due to SEI formation, irreversible side reactions and the limited reversibility of Li^+ ion extraction, results in a low initial coulombic efficiency (ICE) of 8.1%⁷². During subsequent cycles, the ZrS_3 electrode exhibit minor capacity fade, maintaining a discharge capacity of 33.5 mAh g^{-1} after 40 cycles (**Fig. 3g**). This fade may be attributed to electrolyte decomposition, SEI stabilization, and persistent side reactions between Li^+ and ZrS_3 ⁶⁷. These findings indicate that the 1.0–3.0 V range primarily supports intercalation reactions, contributing to stable but modest capacity retention during cycling. In the 0.3–3.0 V voltage range, both intercalation and partial conversion reactions contribute to the electrochemical performance of the ZrS_3 electrode. As shown in **Fig. 3e**, the initial discharge and charge capacities reach 795 mAh g^{-1} and 287 mAh g^{-1} , with 36.1% ICE, which is notably higher than that of the 1.0–3.0 V range. A discharge plateau at 0.3 V is observed, suggesting that partial conversion reactions occur with moderate reversibility. However, structural changes and gradual electrode

reorganization may still lead to capacity fading over cycling, as confirmed by **Fig. 3h**. This voltage range allows for deeper lithiation, initiating partial conversion where ZrS_3 begins decomposing into metallic Zr and Li_2S , though without complete conversion⁷³. This partial reaction provides additional lithium storage sites beyond those accessible by intercalation alone, yielding a discharge capacity of 241 mAh g^{-1} after 40 cycles. Importantly, because complete conversion is avoided, the structural stability of the electrode is preserved. This range thus benefits from both the reversible intercalation process and partial conversion reactions, achieving a balance of increased capacity and structural integrity⁷⁴. In the 0.001–3.0 V voltage range, both intercalation and conversion reactions dominate, resulting in high initial discharge and charge capacities of 1946 mAh g^{-1} and 930 mAh g^{-1} , with an ICE of 47.8%. This broad voltage range allows for extensive conversion reactions, significantly increasing capacity relative to narrower voltage windows. The sustained discharge plateau at 0.3 V in subsequent cycles highlights the partial reversibility of conversion reactions, as observed in **Fig. 3f**. The ZrS_3 electrode retains a discharge capacity of 844 mAh g^{-1} after 40 cycles (**Fig. 3i**), reflecting moderate capacity retention, though some degradation may result from the irreversible nature of the conversion reaction and incomplete reoxidation of Li_2S ⁷⁵.

To investigate the structural evolution of ZrS_3 during cycling, *ex-situ* XRD measurements were performed at different voltage windows (1.0–3.0 V, 0.3–3.0 V, and 0.001–3.0 V), as shown in **Fig. S1**. The results reveal voltage-dependent peak shifts and partial reversibility, indicating a predominant intercalation mechanism with limited conversion reactions. (Details are provided in the Supplementary Information.) The in-plane polar diagram of the Young's modulus plots of bulk ZrS_3 before and after lithiation is illustrated in **Fig. S2**. The results indicate that the Young's modulus of lithiated LiZrS_3 is significantly higher than that of pristine bulk ZrS_3 in all directions,

implying outstanding mechanical stability during lithium intercalation and deintercalation processes. These results collectively support the comprehensive evaluation of the structural evolution and electrochemical performance of ZrS_3 across the 0.001–3.0 V window. This range captures both high-voltage intercalation processes, which contribute to reversible lithium storage, and low-voltage conversion reactions, which primarily involve structural transformations of ZrS_3 into Zr and Li_2S . These processes offer a full assessment of the performance of the material, since they cover the entire range of potential reactions that influence capacity, stability, and structural changes over cycling. By investigating this broader window, a more complete picture of the underlying mechanisms can be obtained, which is critical for optimizing ZrS_3 as an anode material for lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) ⁷⁶.

Fig. 3 Electrochemical performance evaluation of ZrS₃ electrodes in lithium coin cells in the voltage ranges of 1.0–3.0 V, 0.3–3.0 V, and 0.001–3.0 V: (a–c) Cyclic voltammetry curves at a scan rate of 0.2 mV s⁻¹; (d–f) Charge/discharge profiles for selected cycles at a current density of 50 mA g⁻¹; (g–i) Cycling performance over 40 cycles.

To investigate the morphological and compositional evolution of the ZrS₃ electrode during cycling, *ex-situ* SEM, SEM-EDX, and cross-sectional SEM analyses were performed at different cycle numbers under varying current densities. The results for 0–100 cycles at 100 mA g⁻¹ are displayed in **Fig. 4** and **Table 2**. SEM micrographs at high magnifications reveal a relatively smooth electrode surface with no significant aggregation after 0 cycles (**Fig. 4a**), 1 cycle (**Fig. 4b**) and 10 cycles (**Fig. 4c**). However, after 100 cycles (**Fig. 4d**), the surface becomes rougher with small aggregated features, indicating gradual surface reconstruction. SEM-EDX mapping (**Fig. 4e–h**) indicates a homogeneous distribution of O across the electrode surface. With increased cycling (10 and 100 cycles, **Fig. 4g** and **4h**), the oxygen signal intensifies, suggesting progressive accumulation of SEI components or partial surface oxidation, possibly forming ZrO₂. This oxidation process may originate from continuous exposure to trace moisture or residual oxygen in the electrolyte, and is commonly observed in sulfide-based electrodes. Cross-sectional SEM (**Fig. 4i–l**) reveals that the electrode thickness initially increases from ~46 μm to ~65 μm, likely due to SEI formation and electrolyte infiltration, and then gradually decreases to ~51 μm upon extended cycling. This trend indicates electrode densification and interfacial compaction over time, rather than irreversible expansion or mechanical pulverization. Such structural stabilization is beneficial for long-term cycling performance. Detailed observations, including surface roughening, partial oxidation, and electrode thickness changes, are summarized in the Supporting Information.

Fig. 4 Morphological evolution of ZrS_3 electrodes during cycling at 100 mA g^{-1} (0.001–3.0 V). (a–d) Top-view SEM images at high magnifications after 0, 1, 10, and 100 cycles. (e–h) O $\text{K}\alpha_1$ elemental mappings after 0, 1, 10, and 100 cycles. (i–l) Cross-sectional SEM images after 0, 1, 10, and 100 cycles.

To further elucidate the structural evolution of ZrS_3 during deep cycling, additional *ex situ* XRD measurements were conducted over a voltage range of 0.001 V to 3.0 V across two full discharge/charge cycles, as illustrated in **Fig. 5a**. This extended analysis provides a more

comprehensive understanding of the phase transformations occurring during extreme lithiation and delithiation. By systematically tracking diffraction pattern changes at 13 distinct voltage states (A–L), we gain deeper insights into the interplay between intercalation and conversion reactions. The XRD analysis indicates that ZrS_3 undergoes both intercalation and conversion reactions, consistent with reported behaviors of layered transition metal sulfides like ZrS_2 ^{77,78}.

As shown in **Fig. 5b**, the diffraction peak at $\sim 9.6^\circ$ corresponding to the (001) plane of ZrS_3 remains nearly unchanged between the open-circuit voltage (OCV, state A) and 1.84 V (state B), indicating a lithium intercalation-dominated process with minimal structural distortion. Upon further discharge to 0.89 V (state C) and 0.23 V (state D), this peak gradually vanishes, signaling the onset of a conversion reaction that disrupts the layered framework. Interestingly, a new diffraction peak emerges at $\sim 43.6^\circ$ (**Fig. 5b**, right panel) during deep discharge (state D), attributed to the formation of Li_2S or metallic Zr⁶⁷. This peak fades during charging (states F–G) and is completely absent in the second-cycle stages (states I–L), highlighting the partial irreversibility of the conversion process. Upon recharging to 3.0 V (state H), the (001) peak at $\sim 9.6^\circ$ partially reappears, suggesting partial reconstruction of the ZrS_3 framework. However, the overall XRD pattern does not fully return to its initial state, evidencing incomplete structural reversibility. During the second cycle, XRD patterns recorded at 0.86 V (state I) and 0.001 V (state J) confirm partial lithiation and structural reformation. However, the intensities of the main peaks remain significantly altered compared to those in the pristine state. At 1.09 V (state K) and 3.0 V (state L), further lithium extraction improves crystallinity but still fails to fully restore the initial structure. These results collectively support a dual lithium storage mechanism involving both intercalation and conversion, with irreversible phase changes contributing to capacity fading. This *ex situ* XRD analysis provides

valuable insights into the challenges associated with achieving full reversibility and stable cycling performance in ZrS₃-based electrodes.

To further elucidate the lithium intercalation behavior of ZrS₃ and validate its structural anisotropy, *in situ* optical microscopy and time-resolved Raman spectroscopy were performed. Bulk ZrS₃ was mechanically exfoliated and stamped onto a Si/SiO₂ substrate, which was repeatedly immersed into a 1 mM solution of lithium anthracenide for various time periods. **Fig. 5c** displays the optical images captured during lithiation and the corresponding time-resolved Raman spectra. Since ZrS₃ exhibits pronounced anisotropic properties, the Raman spectrum was acquired from a ZrS₃ flake oriented at an approximate 45° angle, ensuring the presence of primary Raman modes. The Raman signal collected from the pristine ZrS₃ flake marked with a red rectangle with a thickness of ca. 30 nm demonstrated four characteristic Ag vibrations at 150 cm⁻¹, 280 cm⁻¹, 318 cm⁻¹ and 528 cm⁻¹. Upon intercalation, peaks started to shift to lower energy values. Remarkably, we noticed that intercalation propagated exclusively along the a-direction, which is well seen in the images taken at 150 and 210 seconds of intercalation. After 210 seconds, three modes of pristine ZrS₃ had shifted, namely, the peak I-Ag shifted by 1 cm⁻¹ to a lower energy value of 149 cm⁻¹, the peaks II-Ag and III-Ag were significantly widened and both shifted by 5 cm⁻¹, while the peak IV-Ag had diminished. We attribute the different influence of intercalation on intercalated ZrS₃ vibrational modes to the quasi-one-dimensional nature of this crystal. The I-Ag vibration is dominated by the interlayer interaction, while III-Ag and IV-Ag are affected by both the inter- and intralayer interactions⁷⁹, which is reflected in the shift of these modes upon intercalation due to the crystal lattice expansion. The observed phonon behavior thus reflects lattice expansion and vibrational perturbation along specific crystallographic directions, providing additional vibrational evidence for the directional intercalation process proposed in the reaction mechanism.

Fig. 5 (a) Real-time galvanostatic discharge/charge profile of the ZrS₃ electrode with labeled sampling points (A–L) marked for *ex situ* XRD analysis. (b) Zoomed-in *ex situ* XRD patterns of the ZrS₃ electrode showing peak evolution at around 9.6° and 43.6°. (c) Time-resolved optical and Raman spectroscopy analysis of lithium intercalation in ZrS₃ flakes.

To thoroughly evaluate the high-rate electrochemical performance of the ZrS₃ electrode, a systematic investigation was conducted across a range of high current densities, as shown in **Fig.**

6. The electrode was initially activated at a low current density of 25 mA g^{-1} , facilitating complete lithiation and stabilizing the electrode structure. Following this activation, the current density was sequentially increased to 1500, 2000, 2500, and 3000 mA g^{-1} . After reaching the peak current density, the current was progressively reduced back to 1500 mA g^{-1} . **Fig. 6a** presents the galvanostatic charge/discharge potential profiles of the ZrS_3 electrode at selected cycles. The electrode delivered an initial discharge capacity of 415 mAh g^{-1} , with an ICE of 83.8%, partly attributed to irreversible activation processes. The 5th charge/discharge profile shows overlapping curves in subsequent cycles, demonstrating the high reversibility and structural stability of the lithium storage reaction throughout extended cycling. The ZrS_3 electrode display high discharge capacities of 329, 311, 295, and 281 mAh g^{-1} at current densities of 1500, 2000, 2500, and 3000 mA g^{-1} , respectively (**Fig. 6b**). Upon returning to 1500 mA g^{-1} , the capacity recovered to 338 mAh g^{-1} , highlighting both excellent rate capability and structural integrity. To further evaluate the rate response of the electrode, a non-reversible rate test (without current return) was conducted from 25 to 3000 mA g^{-1} (**Fig. S6**). Rate-dependent impedance spectra collected after 10 cycles (**Fig. S7**) revealed progressive increases in interfacial resistance (R_{SEI} and R_{ct}) with increasing current, indicating kinetic limitations at high rates. The corresponding fitted parameters are summarized in **Table S3**, based on the equivalent circuit shown in **Fig. S7e**.

The ZrS_3 electrode exhibits outstanding cycling stability even under high current density of 3000 mA g^{-1} , as demonstrated in **Fig. 6c**. The initial capacity of 347 mAh g^{-1} gradually declines to 265 mAh g^{-1} by the 400th cycle, primarily due to SEI formation and initial lithium consumption.⁸⁰ Subsequently, the capacity slowly recovered and stabilized around 362 mAh g^{-1} by the 1500th cycle, suggesting progressive interfacial stabilization. Remarkably, a continuous increase in capacity was observed during prolonged cycling, reaching 408 mAh g^{-1} at the 2300th cycle, a

behavior rarely reported under such high-rate conditions. This unexpected improvement can be ascribed to the continuous electrode activation, enhanced ionic/electronic conductivity, and potential interfacial reconfiguration.

The EIS spectra at 3000 mA g^{-1} (**Fig. 6d**) support this observation. As shown in **Fig. 6e**, the fitted R_{SEI} and R_{ct} values exhibit a dynamic yet well-coordinated evolution. R_{SEI} remained relatively stable during the first 100 cycles ($10\text{--}12 \Omega$), followed by a moderate increase to $\sim 17 \Omega$ at the 1000th cycle, and a further rise to $\sim 53 \Omega$ at the 3000th cycle, suggesting progressive SEI accumulation. In contrast, R_{ct} initially fluctuated between $32\text{--}44 \Omega$, then rose to 84Ω at 1000 cycles, but decreased again to $\sim 21 \Omega$ at 3000 cycles, indicating interfacial activation and re-established charge-transfer pathways at extended cycling. These impedance trends reinforce the hypothesis of long-term interfacial reorganization, where the growth of SEI is balanced by improved electronic/ionic transport, leading to enhanced capacity retention. The corresponding impedance fitting parameters are summarized in Table S5 of the Supporting Information. These results suggest that ZrS_3 effectively balances Li^+ transport and structural durability, demonstrating excellent long-term cycling performance at high current densities. The corresponding impedance fitting parameters are summarized in **Table S4** of the Supporting Information. While the rate capability remains stable up to 2300 cycles, slight capacity fluctuations beyond this point led to the truncation of **Fig. 6c**. Nonetheless, EIS measurements were extended to 3000 cycles to assess the evolution of interfacial properties at later stages.

To understand the structural integrity and surface evolution of the ZrS_3 electrode, *ex-situ* SEM, SEM-EDX, XPS, and cross-sectional SEM analyses were conducted after 3000 cycles under 3000 mA g^{-1} (**Fig. S4–S5**). XPS spectra (**Fig. S4**) provide additional insights, showing a slight shift in the Zr 3d peak, suggesting limited ZrO_2 formation. These results confirm that despite interfacial

changes, the electrode retains its structural framework, contributing to stable performance. The SEM micrographs (**Fig. S5a**) reveal that, despite minor surface roughening and moderate aggregation, the electrode remains mechanically stable, with no significant cracks. SEM-EDX analysis (**Fig. S5b**) indicates a gradual increase in oxygen content and a corresponding decrease in sulfur intensity, suggesting mild oxidation of the ZrS_3 surface. Cross-sectional SEM images (**Fig. S5c**) further confirm that the electrode maintains a well-retained active material layer, ensuring efficient Li^+ transport and high electrochemical reversibility. A notable capacity decay was observed at $60\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (**Fig. S8**), confirming the thermal instability of ZrS_3 under harsh cycling conditions.

Fig. 6 Electrochemical evaluation of the ZrS₃ electrode in lithium coin cells: **(a)** Galvanostatic charge/discharge voltage profiles at current densities of 1500, 2000, 2500, and 3000 mA g⁻¹. **(b)** Rate capacity and Coulombic efficiency (right Y-axis) vs. cycle number. **(c)** Long-term cycling

performance at 3000 mA g⁻¹. (d) EIS spectra recorded at the 1st, 10th, 100th, 1000th, and 3000th cycles. (e) Evolution of R_{SEI} and R_{ct} derived from EIS fitting at selected cycles.

To further elucidate the kinetic characteristics of the ZrS₃ electrode, cyclic voltammetry (CV) measurements were systematically performed over a range of scan rates from 0.4 to 20 mV s⁻¹, as illustrated in **Fig. 7a**. In electrochemical systems, charge storage generally consists of two components: faradaic (diffusion-controlled) processes, which involve charge transfer reactions, and non-faradaic (surface-controlled) contributions, such as double-layer capacitance. These components can be analyzed by evaluating redox peak currents (*i*) at varying scan rates (*v*) using the following relationships:

$$i(V) = a v^b \quad (3)$$

$$\log i(V) = \log a + b \log v \quad (4)$$

In these equations, *a* and *b* are constants where the value of *b* provides insight into the charge storage mechanism. A *b* value close to 1 suggests surface-controlled, capacitive behavior, while a value around 0.5 indicates a diffusion-limited process⁸¹.

The plots of $\log i$ versus $\log v$ in **Fig. 7b** reveal slopes, or ‘*b*’ values, of approximately 0.7466 for the reduction peak (R) and 0.5992 for the oxidation peak (O). These values suggest that the charge storage in ZrS₃ involves a combination of both capacitive (surface-driven) and diffusion-limited behaviors, with capacitive processes being more dominant. Specifically, The *b* value for the anodic peak 0.7466 highlights a hybrid storage mechanism: capacitive contributions arise from the high specific surface area of the porous structure of ZrS₃, which promotes rapid Li-ion adsorption on the electrode surface, while the bulk of the material supports diffusion-controlled lithium storage. This dual mechanism of charge storage indicates efficient Li⁺ kinetics and rapid charge transfer

near the electrode surface, contributing to the enhanced electrochemical performance and stability of the ZrS₃ electrode in lithium-ion battery applications.

The coexisting capacitance-controlled and diffusion-controlled processes in the ZrS₃ electrode are characteristic of complex electrochemical reactions, each contributing uniquely to overall lithium storage. These contributions can be quantitatively assessed using the following relationship:

$$i(V) = k_1v + k_2v^{0.5} \quad (5)$$

In this equation, the terms k_1v and $k_2v^{0.5}$ represent the capacitance-controlled (surface-driven) and diffusion-controlled (bulk-driven) contributions, respectively. The parameters k_1 and k_2 are determined by rearranging the **Equation 6** to analyze the plot of $i(V)/v^{0.5}$ versus $v^{0.5}$.

$$\frac{i(V)}{v^{0.5}} = k_1v^{0.5} + k_2 \quad (6)$$

Here, the slope of this plot represents k_1 , indicating the extent of surface-controlled behavior, while the y-intercept corresponds to k_2 , revealing the diffusion-controlled contribution. By selecting a scan rate of 2.0 mV s⁻¹, the capacitance-controlled contribution for the ZrS₃ electrode was calculated to be 77.67%, as illustrated in **Fig. 7c**. This substantial capacitance contribution suggests that lithium-ion storage in ZrS₃ is largely influenced by pseudocapacitive effects, which enable both rapid and stable Li⁺ uptake, especially at higher current densities.

Fig. 7d reveals the distribution of capacitive and diffusion-controlled contributions over a range of scan rates from 0.4 to 20.0 mV s⁻¹. With increasing scan rate, the contribution from capacitance-controlled processes progressively rises from 25.58% at the lowest scan rate to 89% at the highest, highlighting the strong rate capability of the ZrS₃ electrode. This trend highlights the 2D layered structure of the electrode, which facilitates rapid electron transfer and Li⁺ diffusion by providing ample active surface sites and shorter ion transport pathways. These structural advantages enable efficient lithium storage, demonstrating that the ZrS₃ electrode is well-suited for high-power

applications due to its promising rate performance and stability under varying charge/discharge conditions.

Fig. 7 Electrochemical kinetics of the ZrS_3 electrode: **(a)** Cyclic voltammetry (CV) profiles at various scan rates; **(b)** Linear relationship between $\log(i)$ and $\log(v)$ for each redox peak, illustrating reaction kinetics. **(c)** Capacitive and diffusion-controlled contributions at a scan rate of 2.0 mV s^{-1} . **(d)** Normalized capacitive contribution and the diffusion-controlled contribution fractions across various scan rates.

The diffusion pathways and energy barriers of Li^+ in bulk and monolayer ZrS_3 were calculated using the CI-NEB method, as shown in **Fig. 8a–c**. The results indicate that Li^+ migrates between

two adjacent stable H-sites *via* intermediate T-sites, overcoming energy barriers of 0.12 eV in bulk and 0.33 eV in monolayer ZrS₃, respectively. This suggests that bulk ZrS₃ offers faster Li⁺ transport kinetics, which contributes to its superior charge–discharge rate performance observed experimentally. Notably, this trend is contrary to many conventional layered materials where monolayers typically facilitate faster ion transport^{82,83}. The enhanced diffusion in bulk ZrS₃ reveals a unique structural advantage that supports both high-rate capability and long-term cycling stability, highlighting its promise as a high-performance anode material.

Fig. 8 (a) Li-ion diffusion energy barriers in bulk and monolayer ZrS₃, (b) diffusion pathway in bulk ZrS₃, (c) diffusion pathway in monolayer ZrS₃.

Conclusion

2D ZrS₃ microbelts with a quasi-1D structure were synthesized *via* a straightforward solid-state reaction and evaluated as a promising anode material for lithium-ion batteries. This study systematically investigated the electrochemical reaction mechanisms of ZrS₃ under different discharge cut-off voltages (1.0, 0.3, and 0.001 V), distinguishing between intercalation and conversion reactions. The morphological and compositional evolution during these electrochemical reactions were further examined using *ex-situ* XRD, SEM, SEM-EDX, cross section SEM XPS and EIS analysis. It was found that the ZrS₃ electrode exhibits a reversible

intercalation process above 1.0 V, with conversion reactions initiating around 0.3 V. Upon discharge to 0.001 V, full conversion to a mixed phase of amorphous and crystalline components, including Li_2S and Zr, occurs. Interestingly, the original ZrS_3 structure is partially recoverable upon recharging, though with reduced crystallinity relative to the pristine state. These findings were confirmed by *ex-situ* XRD characterizations across various voltage ranges, demonstrating that layered ZrS_3 can accommodate significant lithium-ion storage through multi-step intercalation and conversion mechanisms. The ZrS_3 electrode exhibited excellent lithium storage performance, including a high reversible capacity, superior rate capability (a stable discharge capacity of 281 mAh g^{-1} at a high current density of 3000 mA g^{-1}), and outstanding long-term cycling stability (408 mAh g^{-1} at 3000 mA g^{-1} over 2300 cycles). This superior performance can be attributed to (1) the isotropic characteristics of the mesoporous products formed during initial lithiation, which stabilize the electrode structure; (2) fast pseudocapacitive redox processes that enhance kinetics; and (3) low charge transfer resistance, which facilitates efficient electron and ion transport. To support this interpretation, density functional theory (DFT) calculations were performed to evaluate the Li-ion diffusion behavior. The calculated diffusion barriers for Li^+ in bulk and monolayer ZrS_3 were 0.12 eV and 0.33 eV, respectively, indicating favorable ion transport kinetics. These theoretical results are consistent with the experimentally observed high rate capability and confirm the intrinsic structural advantages of ZrS_3 for rapid and reversible Li-ion storage. Surface-sensitive XPS analysis reveals progressive interfacial changes in Zr, S, and O environments, evidencing current-dependent SEI evolution and electrode surface reconstruction during extended cycling. These findings highlight the potential of ZrS_3 as an anode material for high-performance LIBs, particularly in applications demanding high rate capability and cycling stability. While further optimization of the ZrS_3 electrode is necessary, this study provides crucial insights into the

electrochemical behavior and structural design of ZrS₃, guiding future research on advanced LIB anode materials.

4 Experimental section

4.1 Chemicals

Carbon black (CB, Super P, Alfa Aesar), poly (vinylidene fluoride) (PVDF, Sigma-Aldrich), N-methylpyrrolidone (NMP, 99.7%, Sigma-Aldrich), and ethanol (C₂H₅OH, 99.8%, Sigma-Aldrich) were of analytical grade and directly used. The 1.0 M lithium hexafluorophosphate (LiPF₆) solution mixed with ethylene carbonate (EC), dimethyl carbonate (DMC), diethyl carbonate (DEC) (V: V: V = 1:1:1) with 1.0 % vinylene carbonate (VC) was procured from Sigma-Aldrich.

4.2 Synthesis of zirconium trisulfide (ZrS₃)

ZrS₃ microbelts were synthesized through a direct reaction between zirconium (Zr) and sulfur (S). In a typical procedure, 0.01 mol of Zr powder and 0.03 mol of S powder were uniformly mixed in a mortar and then transferred to a quartz tube. All operations were conducted in an Ar-filled glove box to maintain an inert atmosphere. The quartz tube was subsequently sintered at 500 °C for 72 hours to produce ZrS₃ crystals. The synthesized ZrS₃ materials were directly used for electrode preparation without further processing.

4.3 Computational details

The first principles calculations were performed by using density functional theory (DFT) implemented in the Vienna *ab initio* simulation package (VASP)^{84,85}. The exchange–correlation function was described by using the Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof (PBE) of generalized gradient approximation (GGA)⁸⁶. The energy cutoff point of the plane wave basis was set to 650 eV. A $2a \times 3b \times 1c$ supercell with three-dimensional periodic boundary conditions was created for bulk ZrS₃, and a $2a \times 3b$ monolayer of ZrS₃ with 20 Å vacuum along the *c*-direction was created for

monolayer ZrS₃. Each atom in the unit cell was completely relaxed until the force on each atom was less than 0.01 eV/Å⁻¹, and the electronic self-consistent convergence was set to 10⁻⁶ eV. The Γ -centered 3×3×1 k -point grid and 3×3×4 k -point grid were used for 2D sheet and bulk ZrS₃, respectively. The van der Waals (vdW) interactions was corrected by using the DET-D3 method in bulk ZrS₃ lattice optimization⁸⁷. The calculation of elastic constants was using stress-strain relationships and the Brillouin-zone (BZ) sampling was carried out with a 5×5×6 Γ -centered k mesh. The method of climbing-image nudged elastic band (CI-NEB) was applied to examine the diffusion pathways and diffusion barriers⁸⁸.

4.4 Material characterization

X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns of the ZrS₃ samples were obtained from Bruker D8 Advance Diffractometer (Germany) with Cu K α radiation between 2 θ angles from 5° to 80° with a scanning step size of 0.02°.

The morphology of ZrS₃ after synthesis was analysed using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) with a field emission gun (FEG) electron source (Tescan LYRA dual-beam microscope) at an accelerating voltage of 10 kV. Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) was employed for elemental composition analysis and mapping, using an 80 mm² silicon drift detector (SDD) (Oxford Instruments) and Aztec Energy software at an accelerating voltage of 10 kV. The bulk material was deposited on carbon tape and examined without any modifications.

Changes in electrode thickness during cycling were also examined using a Tescan MAIA dual-beam microscope under identical conditions. For cross-sectional analysis, the electrodes were first immersed in liquid nitrogen for cutting and then transferred to carbon tape for SEM observation. EDX analysis was performed at 15 kV using the same detector and software.

Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) micrographs were acquired using a JEOL JEM-1010 instrument at an accelerating voltage of 200 kV. Images were captured with an SIS MegaView III digital camera (Soft Imaging Systems) and analyzed using AnalySIS v. 2.0 software. A suspension of ZrS₃ was prepared, and the samples were drop-cast onto TEM grids (Cu, 200 mesh, Formvar/carbon, TED PELLA, Inc.) and dried overnight at room temperature.

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) analysis was carried out on using an Omicron Nanotechnology Ltd instrument (Germany) equipped with a monochromatic Al X-ray radiation source ($K\alpha_1=1486.7$ eV). Raman spectroscopy was conducted using a Renishaw inVia system (UK) equipped with a charge-coupled device detector and a 532 nm green DPSS laser, with an output power of 50 mW. Measurements were performed under ambient conditions using a 20 \times objective lens, with each acquisition set to a 10-second integration time and a laser power of 10 mW. The specific surface area and pore size distribution were measured using a BET analyzer (NOVAtouch 2200, USA) through nitrogen physisorption at 77 K.

4.5 Battery assembly and electrochemical measurements

The electrode slurry was prepared by combining the active material (70 wt%), CB conductive additive (20 wt%), and PVDF binder (10 wt%) in NMP solvent. Subsequently, the homogeneous slurry was coated onto a copper foil current collector with a thickness of 7 μm using a laboratory doctor blade. The coated slurry was then dried in a heat pad oven at 70 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 12 h. The dried electrode was punched into 10 mm diameter wafers for use with the loading mass of 1.5–2.2 mg cm^{-2} . A metallic lithium (Li) was employed as counter electrode. Glass microfiber film (Whatman, Grade GF/D) was used as the separator. The electrolyte was 1.0 M LiPF₆ in a mixed solvent (EC/DMC/DEC) with a volume ratio of 1/1/1 (v/v/v) and 1.0 % VC. Two-electrode lithium cells

were assembled using CR2025 coin cells from MTI Corporation in an argon-filled glovebox (MBRAUN, Germany, oxygen and water contents < 0.1 ppm).

Cyclic voltammetry (CV) measurements on the ZrS₃ electrode were performed at a scan rate of 0.2 mV s⁻¹, covering a voltage range from 1.0 to 3.0, 0.3 to 3.0, 0.001 to 3.0 V vs. Li⁺/Li. Multiple CV tests were conducted at scanning rates ranging from 0.4 to 20.0 mV s⁻¹. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) measurements were performed under various conditions, including open circuit voltage (OCV) and after 10 cycles at different current densities (1500, 2000, 2500, and 3000 mA g⁻¹). The measurements were conducted by applying an AC voltage with an amplitude of 10 mV across a frequency range from 100 kHz to 100 mHz. The impedance spectra were obtained and analyzed using Nyquist plots. Data processing and fitting of the impedance spectra were carried out using Nova 2.1 software and ZView 2 software, respectively. CV measurements, coupled with EIS, were performed on the same coin cell to investigate the electrochemical behavior of the ZrS₃ electrode. The tests were conducted using an Autolab PGSTAT204 workstation (Eco Chemie, Utrecht, Netherlands), which provided the necessary data for both CV and EIS analysis.

The cycling behavior and rate capability of the ZrS₃ electrodes were investigated in CR2025 coin cells, operating within a voltage range of 1.0–3.0, 0.3–3.0, 0.001–3.0 V vs. Li⁺/Li. The cycling test comprised 40 cycles, with each cycle conducted at a current density of 50 mA g⁻¹. In addition to the cycling test, rate performance measurements were performed to evaluate the electrochemical behavior of the ZrS₃ electrode. The ZrS₃-based cells underwent cycling at a series of current densities: 25, 1500, 2000, 2500, and 3000 mA g⁻¹. Following the maximum current density of 3000 mA g⁻¹, the current density was gradually decreased in reverse steps down to 1500 mA g⁻¹, with each step consisting of 10 cycles to assess the stability and rate capability of the electrode.

The electrode was initially activated at 25 mA g⁻¹ for 10 cycles to ensure full lithiation and stabilization. Therefore, this initial activation phase was excluded from the presented data to provide a clear representation of the rate performance of the electrode once steady-state conditions were reached. For assessing long-term cycling stability, the cells were subjected to 3000 cycles at a fixed current density of 3000 mA g⁻¹. Additionally, separate long-term cycling tests were performed over 600 cycles at a current density of 1500 mA g⁻¹, under controlled temperatures of 25 °C and 60 °C, to further examine the impact of temperature on the cycling durability and stability of the ZrS₃ electrodes. All galvanostatic charge–discharge tests were performed at room temperature, utilizing a Neware battery test system (BTX 7.6, Shenzhen, China). Cyclic voltammetry was conducted on a coin cell using an Autolab PGSTAT204 workstation (Eco Chemie, Utrecht, Netherlands).

4.6 Battery disassembly and *ex-situ* characterization

After specific cycling protocols, each assembled coin cell was disassembled in an argon-filled glovebox to prevent exposure to air. The recovered electrodes were carefully rinsed with DMC solvent to remove residual electrolyte and surface impurities. Subsequently, *ex-situ* XRD and XPS characterization was conducted to analyse the structural changes in the electrodes post-cycling. Morphological changes in ZrS₃ after cycling were investigated using SEM with a Tescan MAIA dual-beam microscope at 10 kV. The EDX analysis was performed at 15 kV using the same SDD detector and software. To prepare the samples, the cells were opened, and the electrodes were placed on carbon tape for observation without further modifications.

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Data availability statement

The datasets generated during and/or analyzed during the study are accessible via the Zenodo repository: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15389116>.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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